
237. Beta Cephei variables

THE β Cephei (BCEP) variables are the most massive pulsating stars on the main sequence, and are named after the class's $V = 3.2$ mag prototype β Cephei. They are core H-burning stars, spectral type B0–3 IV–V, with $T_{\text{eff}} = 20\text{--}30\,000$ K, and mass $7 - 20M_{\odot}$. They are characterised by pulsations of small amplitude (typically 0.01–0.3 mag) and short period (typically 0.1–0.3 d). They are also known as Beta Canis Majoris stars – and should not be confused with Cepheid variables.

Discovered from radial velocity variations of β Cephei (Frost, 1902), and later by photometry (Guthnick, 1913), the variations were originally ascribed to a spectroscopic binary, since such rapid stellar variations were unprecedented at the time. But from monitoring of other similar objects, Struve (1955) identified long-term changes in the pulsation amplitude. These were interpreted as a beat effect, and duly explained as the simultaneous presence of radial and non-radial modes with closely separated periods.

THE PHYSICAL MECHANISM responsible for their pulsations remained uncertain for several decades: the κ mechanism, specifically when attributed to the changing ionisation and hence opacity of He (as inferred for Cepheids), would not operate due to their much higher temperatures and ionisation states. Cox (1976) listed nine different possible pulsation mechanisms.

Only in the 1990s, with newly calculated opacities, were the pulsations explained by the κ mechanism, but in this case due to the changing opacity of the iron-peak elements (Kiriakidis et al., 1992; Moskalik & Dziembowski, 1992; Gautschy & Saio, 1993; Dziembowski & Pamiatnykh, 1993). For example, Moskalik & Dziembowski (1992) demonstrated that the fundamental radial mode is unstable, and that the instability persists in non-radial modes of similar and lower frequencies.

Fritzewski et al. (2024) summarises the progressive chronology in identifying their oscillation modes, and in understanding the mode excitation and mode selection (viz. why certain modes are excited to observable amplitudes, and some evolve with time).

DETAILED ASTEROSEISMOLOGY studies started with the 21-year ground-based photometric time series of HD 129929 by Aerts et al. (2004b), which provided evidence for at least six periods. Similar long-term ground-based photometry extended such detailed modelling to ν Eri (Aerts et al., 2004a; Pamyatnykh et al., 2004), θ Oph (Handler et al., 2005; Briquet et al., 2007), 12 Lac (Handler et al., 2006; Desmet et al., 2009), and V2052 Oph (Handler et al., 2012; Briquet et al., 2012). Space-based asteroseismology with MOST, CoRoT and Kepler added a handful of other well-studied examples.

THE NUMBER of known β Cep stars has grown steadily in the past decades. Sterken & Jerzykiewicz (1993) listed 59 secure examples (and 79 candidates), while Stankov & Handler (2005) quoted 93 confirmed (and 77 candidates). Pigulski & Pojmański (2008) found 103 new objects with ASAS-3. Labadie-Bartz et al. (2020) detected 113 (86 new) from KELT. Balona & Ozuyar (2020) identified 327 from TESS, while Eze & Handler (2024) added a further 78 in eclipsing binary systems. Shi et al. (2024) concluded that, allowing for duplicates, the number of known Galactic β Cep stars is about 400.

Various of their properties remain poorly understood. Questions include whether changes in the dominant pulsation period can be explained as evolutionary effects over their short (~ 10 Myr) main-sequence lifetimes as the H fuel is depleted, e.g. in the case of BW Vul (Cowan & Odell, 2018), or σ Sco (Struve et al., 1955; Sterken, 1975; Jerzykiewicz & Sterken, 1984; Pigulski, 1992; Tkachenko et al., 2014). Another is the discrepancy between the dynamical masses in binaries, and model predictions, e.g. for σ Sco (Tkachenko et al., 2014).

OF 1.8 million variable stars in Gaia DR3 (Eyer et al., 2023; Rimoldini et al., 2023), the time-series photometry allowed detection of the dominant mode in around 100 000 intermediate- and high-mass dwarfs (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2023). Of these, 222 were classified as β Cep variables, with dominant frequency in the range $\nu_1 = 3 - 8 \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Fritzewski et al., 2024).

THE GAIA light curves are only sparsely sampled, albeit of high (milli-mag) accuracy, and it is not immediately evident that Gaia could contribute to the identification of such asteroseismic pulsation modes.

But as part of a wider study based on a TESS–Gaia cross-matched (g-mode pulsator) sample comprising 85 313 δ Scuti, 11 636 γ Dor, 3426 slowly pulsating B (SPB) stars, and these 222 β Cep variables, Hey & Aerts (2024) used the first 2 years of the more densely-sampled TESS photometry to independently classify the Gaia DR3 list of non-radial pulsators, including their dominant and secondary pulsation frequencies.

They found that the majority of Gaia classifications are indeed consistent with those from TESS, concluding that ‘*the Gaia photometry is exceptionally accurate for detecting the dominant and secondary frequencies, reaching approximately 80% accuracy in frequency for p- and g-mode pulsators*’. Indeed, for the higher frequency p-modes, they concluded that it is, as yet, unclear whether the Gaia or TESS data is more accurate for measuring the ‘true’ dominant frequency.

Their analysis showed that the g-mode pulsators form a continuous group of variable stars along the main sequence across B, A, and F spectral types, implying that the mode excitation mechanisms for all these pulsators ‘*need to be updated with improved physics*’.

Their Figure 7, shown above, is ‘stacked’ according to the dominant pulsation frequency. In contrast to the multiple ridge-like features for the δ Sct variables (the ridges corresponding to various overtone frequencies), the β Cep sample shows no obvious secondary structures... precisely as expected for these low-order pulsators (Stankov & Handler, 2005).

A parallel study by Shi et al. (2024) identified 155 β Cep candidates using data from TESS and Gaia, of which 83 were confirmed as β Cep pulsators. With magnitudes in the range 8–12 mag, amplitudes of 0.1–55.8 mmag, and pulsation periods 0.06–0.31 d, the Gaia DR3 parallaxes are mostly between 0.2–0.6 milli-arcsec.

ASTEROSEISMIC MODELLING, I should emphasise, targets the measurement of fundamental stellar properties such as internal rotation, age (in terms of core hydrogen mass fraction), core boundary mixing, and even tidal effects in multiple systems (e.g. Bowman, 2020).

Further insights into the physics of these pulsators can be expected from future Gaia data releases, on the basis of an increased sample size, and improved light curves. For example, current theoretical models do not precisely match the observed location of these pulsators in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram (e.g. Bursiens et al., 2020), while numerical computations predict fewer excited modes than those detected from the latest space-based photometry (e.g. Rehm et al., 2024).

More detailed physics in computing excited modes changes the predicted instability regions. This will further constrain phenomena such as the Coriolis effect due to rapid rotation (Szewczuk & Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz, 2017), and radiative levitation due to atomic diffusion, in which the segregation of different elemental isotopes leads to different modes being excited by the opacity mechanism (Rehm et al., 2024).

Another of Gaia’s strengths for asteroseismology is that, compared with the single 600–1000 nm TESS pass-band, Gaia’s multi-colour time series (in G, BP, and RP) assists identification of the spherical harmonic wavenumbers (l, m) which characterise the mode’s geometry (via the inclination of the pulsation symmetry axis). More specifically, mode-dependent perturbations of the stellar flux, and limb darkening, can be derived from the amplitude ratios at the different wavelengths (e.g. Heynderickx et al., 1994; Dupret et al., 2003).

FURTHER analysis of the Gaia sample, interpreted with more extended TESS-based photometry, is given by Fritzewski et al. (2024). They identified the mode degrees for 148 stars and, based on grid modelling, derived mass, convective core mass, and ages for 119. Their location in the HR diagram, constructed from Gaia DR3, is shown below, with the solid black line delineating the instability region for p-modes from Bowman (2020).

